

1 **Phosphatase targeting in Luminal B breast cancer: PPP1R16A.**

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6 Breast cancer can be positive for expression of a hormone receptor (ESR/PGR/AR) or a growth factor
7 receptor (ERBB2). Disease recurrence following disease remission (relapse), resistance to endocrine
8 therapy or otherwise inadequate long-term control of disease are challenges that limit effectiveness of
9 existing drugs that treat luminal A and luminal B disease. Here we utilized whole transcriptome
10 technologies (5, 6) to measure total transcription in the primary tumors of humans with luminal A and
11 luminal B breast cancer. We describe one member of a group of phosphatases up-regulated and
12 differentially expressed in human luminal B breast cancer, PPP1R16A, as a catalytically available
13 phosphatase and candidate therapeutic target for the adjunctive medical treatment of luminal B breast
14 cancer.
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CRISPR-based reverse genetic screening of human luminal A or luminal B organoids or primary tumor cells freshly isolated from patients with luminal subtype breast cancers with limited exposure to artificial culture conditions have not yet been described (7, 8). These genetic technologies, though not yet implemented, when done so will likely facilitate discovery of therapeutic vulnerabilities in luminal A and luminal B hormone receptor positive disease with rapidity and ease.

We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the transcriptome (RNA), and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of humans with breast cancer. This includes the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - subtypes of the primary tumor, including luminal, basal and HER2+ forms, "regional" metastasis to the lymph nodes, metastasis to distant sites, including the lungs, the liver and the brain, and the circulating tumor stem cell. Our hypothesis and working strategy dictates that in the short-run, disease complications and therapeutic limitations are best managed using identification of therapeutic targets by whole transcriptome differential expression analyses (subtraction analysis), and in the long-run, will be enhanced and fully complemented by reverse genetic screening strategies to blindly identify subtype-specific and metastasis-specific therapeutic vulnerabilities augmented by novel immunotherapy approaches. Here we describe one such target identified through study of the hormone receptor positive tumor transcriptome: a phosphatase target that is up-regulated, catalytically available and subtype-specific: PPP1R16A.

Results

Figure 1: PPP1R16A is differentially expressed in luminal B breast cancer.

I. Primary tumors of the breast from humans with breast cancer: luminal B subtype

n=29 luminal A breast cancer

n=30 luminal B breast cancer

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
225203_at	1.46E-02	-2.52	-3.601045	-0.5622545	PPP1R16A	8410/29873	71.8

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the tumors of humans with luminal A breast cancer or luminal B breast cancer (5), we discovered differential expression of protein phosphatase 1 regulatory subunit 16A, encoded by *PPP1R16A* in luminal B breast cancer in humans (**Chart 1**). The expression of PPP1R16A changed more than 70% of the human breast tumor transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 29,873 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of PPP1R16A messenger RNA in luminal B subtype tumors, suggesting up-regulation of PPP1R16A during transformation and lineage specification of the breast to the luminal B breast cancer subtype.

II. Primary tumors of the breast from humans with breast cancer: luminal B subtype

n=50 luminal A breast cancer

n=27 luminal B breast cancer

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
8148888	2.82E-03	-3.0836605	-2.00466	-0.2177674	PPP1R16A	2790/33297	91.1

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors of humans with luminal A breast cancers relative to luminal B cancer in a second microarray dataset (6) from independent

1 investigators and a separate patient cohort, we validated differential expression of PPP1R16A in luminal B
2 breast cancer in humans (**Chart 2**). The expression of PPP1R16A here changed more than 90% of the
3 human breast tumor transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in
4 this case, 33,297 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of
5 PPP1R16A messenger RNA in luminal B subtype tumors, suggesting up-regulation of PPP1R16A during
6 transformation and lineage specification of the breast to the luminal B breast cancer subtype.

7 Thus, differential and increased expression of PPP1R16A defines the transcriptional landscape of the
8 luminal B breast cancer subtype in humans.

9 **Discussion**

10 Adjunctive treatments in medical oncology limit the emergence of resistant tumor clones during
11 treatment with a second treatment (whether neoadjuvant chemotherapy or a targeted therapy like
12 tamoxifen and letrozole). We recently used primary tumor transcriptome data to identify multiple
13 phosphatases that we deemed candidate therapeutic targets in management of breast cancer, and
14 fortuitously found their decreased expression was specifically linked to superior overall survival in patients
15 with another subtype of breast cancer, HER2+ breast cancer (14, 15). A multi-kinase approach delivered
16 in conjunction with chemotherapies that target dNTP synthesis, replication of the daughter strand and
17 activity at the spindle at anaphase is most likely to be most effective in limiting tumor clone resistance (16).
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Methods

We utilized GSE45827 for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in luminal A and luminal B subtype primary tumors from humans with breast cancer (along with GSE87049 for target validation) using microarray data (published) and R-based computational methods (GEO2R).